

STUDENTS INVARIANT IMPROVEMENT OF THE LEVEL OF HEALTH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CULTURAL CONTENT

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Abstract. In this article the cultural development of the external stimulus, which are the basis of a healthy person educating norms, values, attitudes, and experience in business methods, professional-pedagogical project activities, self-improvement issues is keeping the word in the field.

Keywords: improvement, personal-professional development, cultural development, cultural compatibility, healthy lifestyle, stages, the mastering process, conduct, *akkulturatsiya*, spiritual.

ИНВАРИАНТНОЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ ЗДОРОВЬЯ СТУДЕНТОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ РАЗВИТИЯ КУЛЬТУРНОГО СОДЕРЖАНИЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье держится слово в поле культурного освоения внешних раздражителей, которые являются основой воспитания норм, ценностей, установок и опыта в области деловых методов, профессионально-педагогической проектной деятельности, вопросов самосовершенствования.

Ключевые слова: совершенствование, личностно-профессиональное развитие, культурное развитие, культурная совместимость, здоровый образ жизни, этапы, процесс овладения, поведение, аккультурация, духовность.

Personal safety and future students of the ideological character of its health healthy lifestyle healthy lifestyle and heated looking for the meaning of activities in the process of improvement in the field of health culture as the subjects of moral aims. Pedagogy and psychology of science is known the material collected, the students subjective position *aktuallashtirish* ways indicated. However, the cultural development of the external stimulant of health to maintain the culture of the person as their conduct, activities and communication management internal to the plan to convert the mechanism very little definition quotes. This issue is the studyshda we have the following rules and *ma'lumot* from come out, we have:

1) culture is the form of and also the results of, additionally it to achieve the method of all the signs of your own into the gets, the latter cultural development in the form of more important *atributiv* is a sign of;

2) students health culture, improving process performed, which is healthy for a person of educating the basis, which are norms, values, relationships, experience and activity, the method of active to know, as well as, man's physical and spiritual development of resources which strengthen the living standards of the organization to;

3) stability to improve the defining factors of outlook at the level of the student health culture to improve the complex and multi-stage, healthy a lifestyle cultural process as semantic referral process;

4) pedagogical work out more methods of development healthy person with a nurturing and safe life of the organization to the process, students are individual, copyright in the form of the construction done is, professional-pedagogical activities of the project and of the increase on the natural and cultural conformity to the principle of culture in the world, their place to mark as.

Healthy living lifestyle a phenomenon himself for life activities of actual content in the program as received , who the students personal-professional development of iot - level semantic development of the improvement with separated is. The initial stage of the health culture of mastering, the primary adaptation with associated professional development environment, activities of the execution mechanisms (e.g., installation) with a mean improvement through the life of a new socio-cultural conditions adapted brings. Health culture of mastering the process of content and pedagogical activity in the structure of the norms, values, meanings, treatment methods with to get acquainted, new role and conduct improvement and in general, knowledge accumulation about the person safe conduct and the health train culture is. Such a stage mechanisms:

a) desire as copy to download on the student's educational environment to improve ways of examples in action repeat;

b) the education system in health factors, of ideali, standards and health practice on tizimlashti are knowledge collect;

c) valeologik of mind on previous stereotypes, efforts, activities and new mastering process with communication of a combination as akkulturatsiya is;

D) self- maintaining your stay and self- improvement for an unconscious aspiration irrasional mechanisms.

Health a culture of motivation in the development of this stage of emotions reflektivni bypassing pass, from the outside given the meaning of mastering a method as flow valuation, or it consciously on the basis of a receive to and on the student's development of the semantic structure of the dynamics to add, them a direct imitation , making it by, but the content without changing, binding dialog with improve can. Education is the process of first place in the student health culture is improving at clear. Mastering as a result of the health culture of the content the students to his subjects, him than personal attitude express with closer and understandable it is. Mutual relations system through only "reflektivassimilation at the level of health culture, the initial reproductive form but constitutional and interpretation of the" students of the world and the world with semantic structures and relations develop. Assimilation of the process mechanisms the following own into takes:

a) the identity from out healthy a lifestyle of the necessary terms (norms, from ideals, traditions, activities, methods , and others in the form of) into the plains translate to as ichkilashtirish, perception, cognition through individual property (explain and understand) and cultural form of change; b) the world with the relationship, his subject by reflected sustain; c) "meaning the issue of"to take off activities (sense-consciousness); D)pedagogical activity in various spheres treatment skills improvement; e) personalize.

As it is known, in particular, a healthy generation, nurturing the culture of two different measurements available are: 1) ob'ektivlashganlar package in the form of student development for external conditions that creates antifaktlar; 2) professional and personal residence of the area and development at the time of healthy is a lifestyle in the form of the person 's personal experience, meaning , and sense of active basis to collect. Health to maintain the culture, it mastering at the level of availability directly with the person of understanding, meaning and meaning of the form, make, them in real life approval of the ability with directly associated . Culture adaptation phase from the development phase transition into the process that put regulatory requirements outside the set, (development and assimilation) health to maintain the

culture that would not change personal meaning as active internal reception making with the transition process to occur will, thus, the student, his help with reproduction and adaptation at the level of education in the process participate will. Student development of this level of culture, the versatility of outlook compared to subjects shows,.. It own cultural and educational practice them apply to for sense and meaning of the evaluation, the review 's ability will improve. "Interpretasiya, his back on every subjects always will be, is it the meaning of defines and reads, the subject of assuming earlier rules, combines. Ekzistentsial-ekzistentsial approach elements are, in this culture and in society inner freedom and the root is able to be, as well as, proper cognitive-gnoseologik, methodical and germenektivika are the aspects"[172, 21-page]. This is in regard to the subjects of the activities of the character's personal and professional development level, notably at the level of the education practice at the individual-personal context at the level of three aspects of improvement it depends on. The inner life experience and pedagogy in the historically accumulated knowledge of the development of motivation in the fullness, business methods , and them with associated many facets with a relationship having is.

First of all, the education so it gives the description: the subject of the formation, that is, the subjects know izohli in business "to the truth of access"(In accordance) and meaning for taking the necessary conditions and tools [19-page]. The latter, it appears that the person is "the total experience and knowledge" of the rising represents, because people such does not make. By nature so be should. We in education important thing is the person, his spiritual on the meaning of upgrades like the side about we will talk.

In practice, this self mavhumlash, himself immediate personal desires and needs, personal needs to drift away the ability of means. Interests, personality development of the spiritual energy that determines the general, the universal framework of the special show to an example as to see and understand can. The third aspect of the education phenomenon of the person development of the defining factors of view point provides a description, and his help with it show will and this with along his subjects creates, it konkretlashtirish in the form of it represents. Healthy is a lifestyle of overall experience in itself a form of term subjects of universal konkret existence, its content individuallashtirish to be converted [those here, 230-page]. Students of health in the culture of personal development in this stage the following mechanisms by keeps:

a) the activity of evaluation of life values and their meaning personally himself for the education of subjects as search;

b) know of the emotional and abstract-logical side in the middle "bridges build" the meaning through; c) cultural identification with the health of cultural belonging that to realize;

D) otherwise sustain a method as self- to know pedagogical education of the subject as; e) to select them, health to maintain the culture , values and them sub'ektivlashtirish and others. This stage of the student's subjects and the same on the basis of his individuallik of further expansion. On the outside the student's active developing ijtimoiylashuv to the lens of health improvement activities see in the activity of the manifestation to be added. Own inner world, local and global pedagogy of health to maintain the culture mindset - based self- development and self - self determination of the leading factors is one. Internal resonance and sustain the creative process of the most important structural components in the future the student's self - himself means, their existence konkret look in the way the value of understanding, self- knowing by himself to take care of to be as will enter. Health and safety the importance of business motives stimulating the power of cognitive suction at the level of not, but the process is the

emotional relationship that is. Cognitive activity of this aspect of cognitive and emotional, rational and irrational, and others dialectic of unity into account them to take need on which many psychological and pedagogical research results with shown will be. In so doing, health to maintain the culture of subjects as students circulation mastering the process, its values and norms between the radical difference made increase is based on. Pedagogical standards, the including pedagogical norms companion is, the teacher of the activity of rational foreign given, every time, also done is, regulating in sanitary-gigienik process is. In their turn, values - emotional utilized inside activities, so for that also his spiritual intention as taken will be the record of the subject by that motivated to power ability will be.

Improvement of the outlook for the determinant of seeing in the students health culture as identity, the necessity of the issue is raised and the people of the past from the experience and come out the personal and cultural own specific processes of the unity in the form of the person ijtimoiylashtirish of the most important mechanism is [280, 28-29bet]. Of the person personality in improving the two parties involved that reason, only the representation is not them, but between mutual relationship about the question of the birth is natural. This event is educational aspect of this with the expression, identification of professional self- nurturing a tool to serve the will and its basis of other feelings and the condition with emotional common sense as sempatiyadir [69, 152-page]. Personal accessibility enhanced self- creation of the act, the subjects of creative self- consciousness stage representing human phenomenon is. Yourself for sign installation for self- improvement unlimited process as new claims and achievements of the nest out of, in his "history of the laws" to at mujassamlashtirmasdan stand, in itself, stay, the truth on come and self- out increase the ability to represent.

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